

Recommended citation: Mäkilouko, M. I. (2017). Student Experience and Motivation Industrial Management Masters' Degree Programme . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1013-1018). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698361.

Student Experience and Motivation

Industrial Management Masters' Degree Programme

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ABSTRACT

The Industrial Management Master of Science degree programme at Tampere University of Applied Sciences has a graduation rate of 50 %. The programme is non-conventional adult education but is not distance or online learning programme and has traditional lectures and other class room work. Students' inadequate motivation is expected to be one of the major reasons for low graduation rate. This paper studies student' expectations, motivation and learning experience. The motivation is defined as an incentive element which creates the mental energy to carry out a learning process. The research method was qualitative grounded theory. When we look at the students' studies beginning and end motivators, the goal based motivators that the students started with have been replaced by situational motivators. The motivation level remains high with the clear majority of the students. About half report intrinsic motivation and the other half extrinsic motivation. It looks that we have succeeded in maintaining students' motivation and the low graduation rate cannot be directly explained by low motivation. Thus, the research failed to provide a direct answer for the low graduation rate. On the other hand, it may be asked whether the main source of low graduation rate is the good motivation. Students may be so challenged and motivated by the courses that the thesis work moves to a secondary place.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills

Keywords: University of Applied Sciences, Masters' Degree, Pedagogy of Higher Education, Industrial Management

INTRODUCTION

The Industrial Management Master of Science degree programme at Tampere University of Applied Sciences has existed since 2009. During this time 92 Bachelor of

Science engineers have continued their studies to the higher degree. The student intake has been 180 students. The programme represents non-conventional adult education since the average age at the start of studies is 38,4 years. The programme consists of lectures on Fridays and Saturdays and home work. All students work full time but have an agreement with their employers to take every second Friday off for their school work. This is not distance or online learning, but traditional in the sense of lectures and a permanent body of students organized into a class that meets every second Friday and Saturday. The reduced number of lecture hours is offset with more reading and reporting the reading with essay type book reviews.

The major obstacle for graduation has been various problems with the thesis work. Some part of this obstacle is related to the changes in the employers' organisation but the rest can be helped by actions that we can take at the university. Earlier we have improved the graduation rate by developing thesis supervision as reported in our previous paper. These steps included organising students into thesis supervision groups based on the thesis topic (e.g. project management or financial indicators), and selecting thesis supervisors based on their practical experience with the thesis topic. This improved the guidance the students receive during the thesis work. This paper studies student experience and motivation. The aim is to see whether the university can do more to improve students' motivation which in turn may lead to improved graduation rate.

1 EARLIER RESEARCH

There has been research with regards to student "achievement gap", in which students underperform and don't graduate. Most of this has been in relation to various socio-economic factors. For example, Martin, Galentino and Townsend found that students who had clear goals, strong motivation, managed external demands and who were self-empowered could overcome obstacles and graduate from college. In Finland, socio-economic factors are non-existent so none of these studies are directly comparable. In addition, the programme is non-conventional adult education, research that concentrates on students who are 18 years' younger is most likely not accurate in our case. There are motivational studies regarding distance and online learning, but these are not applicable since we have a traditional student class and only contact learning. Our lectures are not transmitted online. We are left with a very short research review with the lack of relevant earlier research.

The motivation is defined by Illeris as an incentive element which creates the mental energy to carry out a learning process. There are many potential ways to consider motivation, e.g. extrinsic vs. intrinsic or goal vs. situational motivation. We also expect that motivation may not be steady but changes during studies.

2 RESEARCH QUESTION

The research topic is formulated to be student expectations, motivation and learning experience. Rather than assuming steady motivation and motivating factors, we want to find whether the motivation and the motivating factors change during the studies.

The data is collected qualitatively with open topic essays. The research method is grounded theory, which means that there is no research question. The research question is formulated from the collected data, i.e. data leads the research where ever it may go. The grounded theory is suitable when the research aim is only to increase understanding which is precisely the situation here. The findings are coded into categories in a mind map tree. The categories are derived from the data. When the

essays have been coded, single findings are removed and only those with multiple hits are left remaining. The categories are explained and form the research results.

Students were asked during the first term to write an essay about their expectations, motivation and learning experience so far. This is intended to form a baseline. The second time, students are asked to write a similar essay at the end of their studies. When compared to the baseline we can see if there are any changes. This comparison hopefully reveals the motivational issues, failures to meet the expectations and negative and positive learning experiences. This information can be used to improve the programme and hopefully improve the graduation rate.

The topic was broadly explained but students were encouraged to write their own ideas thus reducing the guidance by the researcher. Since the research is so small we didn't use interviews, i.e. some students would both be interviewed and write essays thus the interference by the researcher would only increase.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Beginning of Studies

In the beginning of studies students reported high motivation. The number one motivating factor was career advancement, which was reported by 8 out of 29 students. Four students explained that career needs new skills. The two second highest motivators were that career needs formal qualifications and the job needs more skills. Both were listed at 4 out of 29 students. Two also explained in detail that problems at work need more solutions. The third motivator was the will to learn new things with 3 students. Two students did not list any special motivators, but felt themselves to be very motivated to study. However, two students immediately reported that it is hard to start learning new things. The remaining students reported various other things including programme's good reputation and need for time management. These were reduced out of the mind map tree since they all were single findings. The motivators are collected into Figure 1. The number represents the number of hits per each finding. A total of 21 students out of 30 were left in the mind map tree with multiple findings but all reported some form of motivation.

Fig. 1. Beginning of Studies Motivators

3.2 End of Studies

At the end of studies students' motivation had changed very much as shown in Figure 2. The previous motivators had all disappeared and were replaced by new programme based situational motivators. Also, as expected, some demotivators had appeared. Some students also reported both motivators and demotivators at the same time.

Two students reported increased motivation and explained that they see work and life in a new light. This is the transformal learning experience. Seven students reported decreased motivation. This was the most interesting category for our research. The decreased motivation was all based-on schedule problems. Students explained that school work piles up and family problems increase over time. Three students also reported lack of support from their employer and therefore continuous schedule problems as they were expected to have every second Friday free for lectures.

Twenty students out of 29 reported maintained motivation. This was mostly based on the very good programme. This was further divided into good courses and excellent visiting lecturers. None of the students reported any failures, negatives or failures to meet expectations during the studies. Regarding the university there was nothing negative in all the collected data. Eight students also reported the student group as one source of motivation. In addition, there were numerous other single findings that were reduced out of the mind map tree.

Fig 2. End of Studies Motivators and Thesis Issues

Eight students had made clear decision to postpone their thesis to the second year. Two of them felt that the time should be 1,5 years. The thesis topic had changed during the year with three students and one of the reported that he is now working on the third thesis topic.

4 DISCUSSION

Our results can be considered using Illeris’ three dimensions of learning which is represented in figure 3.

Fig. 3. Fundamental Process of Learning

The content dimension means in practise that the programme must provide challenging and interesting learning content. An individual also must have an incentive to learn, i.e. motivation. Learning is hampered if the incentive and content don't match or if one or both are not provided. The knowledge acquisition happens in the interaction between incentive and content. Since students report high satisfaction with the programme, it would seem that we have managed to provide sufficiently good content for students. At beginning of the studies, students also have personal incentives, although it is no longer so relevant at the end of the studies. However, most students are well motivated so that we can estimate that the incentive to learn still exists.

Environment dimension means in practise that the environment should provide support and supportive positive interaction for the learning experience. It would also seem that we have a good learning environment since 8 students reported a very good team spirit and that students share experiences among themselves. But the environment can be a challenge to some students since 7 students reported decreasing motivation due to time problems and also lack of support from the employer.

It is interesting to note that two students reported transformal learning experience. This, while interesting, is not the topic of this study, but clearly is something that is worth studying further. It may be that we can further develop this programme so much that we can foster more transformal learning.

5 CONCLUSIONS

When we look at the beginning and end motivators, the goal based motivators have been replaced by situational motivators. The motivation level remains high with the clear majority of the students. About half report intrinsic motivation and the other half extrinsic motivation. The assumption that low motivation would explain low graduation rate is not directly supported. The reduced motivation, that was expected to be main source for low graduation rate and delayed thesis, received support only with seven students. Their source of demotivation were the schedule problems which were largely beyond their control. For example, students cannot dictate employer's demands for attendance and effort at work. The schedule problems are hard to solve since studies do need time and effort and therefore one cannot maintain similar family life and presence at work as before, during the studies.

It seems that we have done good work in maintaining students' motivation. If we take a broader glance it seems clear that to maintain students' motivation the university and the programme must provide new motivators during the studies. The goal based motivators in the beginning of studies will not carry very long and cannot maintain sufficient motivation to the end studies.

What is then the reason for low graduation rate? The research failed to provide direct answer. On the other hand, it may be asked whether the main source of the low graduation is good motivation. Students may be so challenged and motivated by the courses that the thesis work moves to a secondary place. The general trend is that our students are not satisfied with low grades but continue extra work until they reach one of the two highest grades (4 or 5). Also, the student satisfaction index which is collected from student feedback and from all programmes at the university is the highest with this programme. In other words learning becomes more important than graduation.

The other possible explanation for low graduation rate may be that many students actually don't need formal credentials. Instead they need more skills to improve their career. Staying at the university and taking more courses is the best possible course of action if you want more and more skills.

At our university, other programmes with a low student satisfaction index and low number of applicants, tend to reach high graduation rate. It may be, that students who don't like the university and their programme, want to get the formal credentials as soon as possible. They get low grades and graduate quickly. Students who like the university and the programme want to stay long, learn as much as possible and do not always graduate. Still they recommend studies to others and we get a lot of applicants.

This small research did not provide help in improving graduation rate. Instead it set in question the idea that good motivation is needed for graduation. We have systematically taken steps to improve motivation and have reached possibly the highest motivation level at the university, but it doesn't help with the low graduation rate problem.

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